

Original Research Report

Perceived Effectiveness of Early Childhood Education, Development and Care in Reducing Family Restiveness by Students and Parents

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Abstract: This paper examined the effectiveness of early childhood development, care, and education as a panacea to family restiveness. Three specific objectives and three research questions were formulated to guide the research. The study was conducted in omoku, using 137 parents from a federal college of education and 163 students from the demonstration secondary school, omoku. The sample size was made up of all 142 parents, and a 5-point Likert scale was used to calculate the mean ratings. The instrument was face validated by three experts, and a reliability coefficient of .831 was achieved. The instrument was face-validated by three experts, and a reliability coefficient of .871 was achieved. The following findings were made from the study: respondents opined that early childhood education, care, and development act as a panacea to family restiveness as it improves a child's intuition, character, understanding, and confidence level. Parents should live up to the responsibility of giving their children the best by sending them to school at an early age.

Keywords: Childhood, Care, Development, Education, Family

1. Introduction

There has been much interest in the effectiveness of different strategies for fostering child development, care and education. Child development is an important determinant of health and reduces family restiveness (Philips et al., 2000). Halfon (2002) observed that the early years of life are a period of considerable opportunity for growth and vulnerability to harm. Children's developmental trajectories are shaped by sources of resilience as well as vulnerability. The cumulative experience of buffers or burdens is a more powerful determinant of children's developmental well-being than single risk or protective factors (Philips et al., 2000). Early developmental opportunities establish a critical foundation for children's academic success, health, and general well-being.

Critical dimensions of child development are self-regulation, the establishment of early relationships, knowledge acquisition, and the development of specific skills (Ansari, 2018; Ansari, & Pianta, 2018). These dimensions are affected by individual neurobiology, relationships with caregivers, and physical and psychosocial exposures in the caregiving environment. The interaction of biology and the social environment exerts a powerful influence on a child's readiness to learn and on success in school, both antecedents to health outcomes in later life (Ansari, 2018; Ansari & Purtell, 2018). In addition to frequently cited risk factors for developmental dysfunction (e.g., premature birth, low birth weight, childhood infections, and lead poisoning), exposure to an economically impoverished environment is recognized as a social risk factor. The socioeconomic gradient in early life is mirrored in cognitive and behavioral development (Ansari, 2018; Ansari, & Pianta, 2018; Ansari, & Purtell, 2018).

Early childhood intervention programs seek to prevent or minimize the physical, cognitive, and emotional limitations of children disadvantaged by poverty (Barnett, 2011). Comprehensive early childhood development programs are designed to improve the cognitive and social-emotional functioning of preschool children, which, in turn, influences readiness to learn in the school setting (Crosnoe, 2007). Low family income and community poverty lead to racial and ethnic achievement gaps (Camilli et al., 2010). A recent U.S. Department of Education study shows, for example, that 71% of white children entering kindergarten could recognize letters, compared with 57% of African-American children (Carlson, 2005).

School readiness, particularly among poor children, may help prevent the cascade of consequences of early academic failure and school behavioral problems: dropping out of high school, delinquency, unemployment, and psychological and physical morbidity in young adulthood. Early childhood education, care and early childhood development have a role to play in family in family restiveness as it may either boost or reduce the following characteristics of a child: character, intuition, understanding and confidence level, this may intern lead to family stability or family restiveness. Early Childhood Education entails the period of learning that takes place from birth to 8 years old. There are several types of early education programs, including those that are federal, state or privately funded. Care entails the provision of what is necessary for the health, welfare, maintenance, and protection of someone or something. Early Childhood Development (ECD) is a period of rapid and critical development - from conception to 8 years. Quality nurturing care during this period - adequate nutrition, good health care, protection, play and early education - is vital for children's physical, cognitive, linguistic and social-emotional development. The present study reviews recent empirical research in order to identify pedagogical strategies that benefit child

development effectively. It summarizes evidence from studies aiming to inform research-based practices in early childhood care and education. In particular, this study looks at strategies that support the development of language, mathematics, and social-emotional skills. Thus, it attempts to determine a set of strategies that form the basis of effective early childhood care and education, providing evidence not only for researchers but also for staff working in the early childhood education sector as well as for policymakers who need practical information about techniques that promote children's skills in various developmental domains effectively.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Families are going through tough times because of attitudes and character displayed by members of the family, especially by children; children are prone to peer pressure and constant abuse from the internet, thereby affecting them psychologically. But it is optimal and equivalent to note that these are not the only streams of concerns raised by parents, in respect to their children and the quality of education their children receives. There's a sudden increase in kidnapping, cultism, prostitution, in Omoku, Rivers State Nigeria, which the researcher believes is caused by lack of early education and care, hence the mental development of this young ones are low. It is imperative to note that it was posited biblically that if you train up a child properly, he cannot and will not depart from it. Although several researchers might disagree with their theory, it is of importance to note that most young ladies and men in Omoku grew up in a polygamous home with an absentee father/mother and they also started going to school around the age of 6-7 years. It is to that effect this research work was birthed, to ascertain the effectiveness of early childhood education, development and care in reducing family restiveness.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of study is to examine of effectiveness of early childhood development, care and education in reducing family restiveness. Specifically, the study intends to:

- (a) Analyze the extent to which early childhood education act as a panacea to family restiveness
- (b) Examine the effectiveness of caring as a panacea to family restiveness
- (c) Ascertain the importance of early childhood development to a family

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study

- (a) To what extent does early childhood education act as a panacea to family restiveness?
- (b) How effective is caring as a panacea to family restiveness?
- (c) How effective is early childhood development to a family?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The study was carried out using a survey design. Survey design deals with the process that provides surveys for identifying, analyzing, and interpreting the relationship between variables that create a particular state of affairs under controlled conditions. Survey design entails collecting data, measuring the opinion and attitudes of the respondents through questionnaire which the results will be generalized upon the entire population (Onyeizugbe, 2013).

2.1.1. Ethics Approval of Research

The researchers sought approval from the management and parents of Ogba comprehensive high school, Omoku. Two professors from the Department of Home Sciences at the Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike and a Principal Lecturer from the Department of Home

Economics Education also vetted the survey to make sure it does not go in contrast with relevant research ethics.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Omoku, the head quarter of Ogba, Egbema, Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Omoku is situated in the Northern part of the State. People from Omoku are referred to as Ogba People. The essence of carrying out this study in omoku was to foster the growth of early childhood education, care and development among parents/guardians so as to increase the relative peace experienced by members of family and the larger society.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population was made up of all 300 parents and children of Ogba comprehensive high school Omoku in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study spanned across the three (3) classes that made the senior secondary section of Ogba comprehensive high school, Omoku. The population consist of hundred and thirty-seven (137) parents in the three classes that made up Ogba comprehensive high school Omoku and one hundred and sixty-three (163) students in of Ogba comprehensive high school, Omoku. The sample size of the study was made up of hundred and forty-two (142) participants (parents and students). The Sample size was derived using Yamane's (1973) formula.

The sample technique used for the study was stratified random sampling technique. This technique was employed to select 102 panelists of students from SS1-SS3 from Ogba comprehensive high school, Omoku. Students within this age group or class were chosen because it is assumed that they were more understanding and more matured to deal with family drama. Also 40 parents of students from the three selected classes were also selected. The average ages of students and parents who responded to the survey are 12 and 38 respectively and a total of 60 female students and 42 male students made up the sample size while a total of 20 females and 20 males made up the sample size of the parents.

2.4. Instrument for Data collection and Study Procedure

A five Point likert Scale questionnaire was constructed by the researchers for data collection. The questionnaire was used to obtain data on the "perceived effectiveness of early childhood development, care and education as a panacea to family restiveness questionnaire" (PEECCEFRQ). The questionnaire was divided into two sections, namely A and B; Section A is the socio economic characteristics of the respondents such as gender and occupation. Section B comprised of items used checking the effectiveness of the variables on family restiveness.

The data were assessed a five point Likert scale

- 5 - - - Extremely Effective (EE)
- 4 - - - Highly Effective (HE)
- 3 - - - Very Effective (VE)
- 2 - - - Slightly Effective (SE)
- 1 - - - Not Effective (NE)

The instrument was validated by three experts in family and human development at the Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike and two lecturers at the Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku. The instrument was tested with five (5) parents and fifteen (15) Students from E2 Genius academy, Nodoro, Abia State. Nigeria. which were not part of the study in order to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. Cronbach Alpha method was used to analyze

the reliability of the instrument and the reliability coefficient of .831 was achieved. Which shows the instrument was very reliable?

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The researchers administered the instrument with the help of two (2) research assistants. The products formulated were given to panelists to use at home to see if they liked it while they responded to the instrument and returned within (3) three days to the researchers. The research assistants were trained by the researchers before embarking on the distribution of the survey.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Data collected from questionnaire were subjected to statistical analysis using STATA 17. Data collected were edited, coded and then entered into STATA data editor. STATA was used to make summaries of data in a way that provided answers to research questions. The data of both respondents were both entered into two different columns of the STATA spread sheet, and was analyzed to ascertain the average mean ratings and standard deviation of our respondents against our variable. Mean rating was used to analyze the research question. Any mean rating greater than equal to or greater than 3.0 was accepted while any mean rating less than 3.0 was rejected. This implies that mean rating higher than or equal to 3.0 depicts the effectiveness of the variable as a panacea to reducing family restiveness whereas any mean rating lesser than 3.0 has negative impact on the family and leads to family restiveness.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Research question one:* How effective is early childhood education as a panacea to family restiveness?

Table 1: Mean rating of early childhood education as a panacea to family restiveness?

Items	X ₁	X ₂	X _g	SD	Remark
Confidence Level	5.0	5.0	5.0	0.00	Extremely Effective
Character	5.0	4.7	4.85	0.21	Highly Effective
Understanding	4.8	4.0	4.4	0.56	Highly Effective
Intuition	4.3	4.2	4.25	0.07	Highly Effective
Pooled Mean	4.75	4.47	4.62	0.21	Highly Effective

Keys: X₁= Mean Response of parents, X₂= Mean Response of students, X_G= Average Mean rating of Both Respondents, SD= Standard Deviation

Table 1 showed that the pooled mean of respondents was as follows parents =4.75, students =4.47 which depicts that both respondents were in consonance on how early childhood education act as a panacea to family restiveness. The standard deviation of 0.21 showed that there was no disparity in agreement among respondents on how early childhood education improves the character, intuition, understanding and confidence level of children who started going to school on time.

3.2. Research question two: How effective is caring as a panacea to family restiveness?

Table 2: Mean rating on how effective is caring as a panacea to family restiveness?

Items	X ₁	X ₂	X _g	SD	Remark
Confidence Level	4.0	5.0	4.75	0.35	Highly Effective
Character	5.0	4.8	4.9	0.14	Highly Effective
Understanding	4.5	4.9	4.7	0.28	Highly Effective
Intuition	4.0	4.8	4.8	0.56	Highly Effective
Pooled Mean	4.4	4.8	4.68	0.26	Highly Effective

Keys: X₁=Mean Response of parents, X₂= Mean Response of students, X_G= Average Mean rating of Both Respondents, SD= Standard Deviation

From Table 2, it was observed that all the items were above the cutoff point of 3.00. This indicates that all the respondents were in agreement that caring for children increases their chance of having a better character, better understanding to family problem, intuition to curb family restiveness before it starts and confidence level to interact with their parents about problems or challenges facing the family. The calculated pooled mean for parents was 4.4 and student 4.8 which is above the decision rule of 3.0. This means that the respondents believe that caring for a child, by showering that child love and affection act as a panacea to reducing family restiveness.

3.3. Research question three: How effective is early childhood development to a family?

Table 3: Mean rating on how effective early childhood development is to family restiveness

Items	X ₁	X ₂	X _g	SD	Remark
Confidence Level	4.0	4.5	4.25	0.35	Highly Effective
Character	4.0	3.0	3.5	0.70	Very Effective
Understanding	4.5	4.5	4.5	0.00	Highly Effective
Intuition	4.6	3.8	4.2	0.70	Highly Effective
Pooled Mean	4.27	3.95	4.11	0.22	Highly Effective

Keys: X₁=Mean Response of parents, X₂= Mean Response of students, X_G= Average Mean rating of Both Respondents, SD= Standard Deviation

From Table 3, it was observed that all the items were above the cutoff point of 3.00. This indicates that all the respondents were in agreement that early childhood development increases their chance of having a better character, better understanding to family problem, intuition to curb family

restiveness before it starts and confidence level to interact with their parents about problems or challenges facing the family. The calculated pooled mean for parents was 4.27 and student 4.11 which is above the decision rule of 3.0. This means that the respondents believe that early childhood development improves a child's perspective and reduces family restiveness.

Accordingly, Barnett (2011) posited that early child education helps in boosting a child's intuitive reasoning which is consonance with the findings of the study. This is also in consonance with the findings Camili et al. (2010) who asserted that early childhood education builds a child's cognitive skills and a child's ability to adapt socially. The research also found out that effectiveness of early care can reduce family restiveness, because a child who is properly taken care of will be a good asset to the society, just like in the bible passage of proverbs 22:6 train up a child in the way he should grow and when he is old he will never depart from you. This finding is in consonance with Ansari (2018) who posited that care goes a long way in guiding a child from early childhood education through adolescence to enable them become better to the society. The limitations of the study were inadequate research material within the country, and the short time frame for the research. The researchers suggest that a research should be carried out on each of the variables, early childhood education, care and development to ascertain the extent to which they affect family restiveness.

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that early childhood development, care and education act as a panacea to curbing family restiveness. For a family to be stable, the parents need to shower more care on their growing kids, send them to school at an early age and make sure they are properly taught in class. Caring for a child requires show of affection. A parent's personal input on the child's welfare and educational development will play a long way in the child's character, intuitive and psychological behaviour. Caring is a very effective tool no doubt for every family to be at peace with another, they must shower love and affection among themselves, parents need to listen more to their kids and try as much as they can provide for their kids. Sending a child early to school helps improves a child intuition hence it is advised that parents invest more on kindergarten education. Parents should provide the enabling environment for their kids to enable them learn and relearn freely, an environment that will enable them to easily interact with their parents. Family needs to learn how to develop themselves, train themselves and care for themselves without any iota of fear of prejudice.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: UCO

Formal analysis: UCO, UEN

Funding acquisition: UCO, UEN

Investigation: UCO, UEN
Methodology: UCO, UEN
Writing – original draft, review & editing: UCO, UEN

Data availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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